

GROUP PARACHORS BY GIBLING'S METHOD. PART I

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The group parachors (C).CH₂.NH₂=83.4, (C).CH₂Cl=95.6, (C).CH₂.Br=108.7 and (C).CH₂I=130.1, have been determined. They have been shown to reproduce experimental results better than Sugden's values. However, it seems that even group parachors are modified by the length of the chain of carbon atoms and also by side chains.

Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299) has suggested a new method of evaluating structural parachors. According to him it is more accurate to substitute group parachors for atomic parachors and structural constants. However, his work was limited to carbon, hydrogen and oxygen atoms and that too, to aliphatic compounds. Bhagwat and Shukla (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 115, 222) have extended this work to aromatic compounds and have determined the values for benzene ring and other groups in aromatic substances. The structural parachors of several other groups, both aromatic and aliphatic, still remain to be determined and unless these values are made known, it is impossible to utilise Gibling's method for the investigation of the unknown or doubtful structures. We have therefore tried to determine the structural parachor of as many groups as possible from the available data. The results used are those given in the list of parachors by British Association for the Advancement of Science (1932).

Structural Parachor of C. CH₂. NH₂ group.

Following structural values by Gibling have been used :

For benzene ring the value = 0, as given by Bhagwat and Shukla (*loc. cit.*), is employed.

In order to determine the parachor of a particular group, several compounds containing that group were taken and their standard values (S. V.) were obtained by subtracting expansion corrections (E. C.) from the observed parachors. When parachors of various groups, except of the group whose parachor is required, are subtracted from the S. V., the group parachor is obtained. The method is illustrated by the following example.

Ethylamine (CH₃.CH₂.NH₂) : $P_{\text{obs}} = 137.4$. E.C. = 0.2.

Hence $S.V. = 137.4 - 0.2 = 137.2$. CH₃.(C) = 55.2.

Hence group parachor for (C).CH₂.NH₂ = 137.2 - 55.2 = 82.0

Table II illustrates that the values calculated by structural parachor method show much better agreement with the experimental values than with the values calculated by Sugden's method.

TABLE I

Compound.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	P for (C).CH ₂ .NH ₂
Ethylamine CH ₃ -CH ₂ .NH ₂	137.4	0.2	CH ₃ -(C)	82.0
<i>n</i> -Propylamine CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₂ .NH ₂	178.5	0.3	CH ₃ -(C) and (C)-CH ₂ -(C)	83.2
<i>iso</i> Butylamine CH ₃ } CH. CH ₂ . NH ₂ CH ₃ }	216.1	0.3	2 CH ₃ -(C) and (C) } CH-(C) (C) }	83.2
<i>ter.</i> Amylamine CH ₃ } C } CH ₃ CH ₃ } C } CH ₂ . NH ₂	252.3	0.5	3 CH ₃ -(C) and (C) } C } (C) (C) }	83.8
Benzylamine C ₆ H ₅ . CH ₂ . NH ₂	273.7	0.7	5 (C)-CH=(C) and (C) } C=(C) (C) }	84.8
				Mean 83.4

TABLE II

Compound.	P (Structural method)	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	P (Sugden's method).
Ethylamine	133.8	137.4	141.8
<i>n</i> -Propylamine	178.7	178.5	180.8
<i>iso</i> Butylamine	216.3	216.1	219.8
<i>ter</i> -Amylamine	251.9	252.3	258.8
Benzylamine	272.3	273.7	275.7

TABLE III

Group parachor for (C)-CH₂.Cl

Compound.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	P for (C). CH ₂ .Cl
Ethyl chloride CH ₃ -CH ₂ .Cl	151.6	0.2	CH ₃ -(C)	96.2
<i>n</i> -Propyl chloride CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ .Cl	190.2	0.3	CH ₃ -(C) and (C)-CH ₂ -(C)	94.9
<i>n</i> -Butyl chloride CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₂ .CH ₂ .Cl	230.5	0.5	CH ₃ -(C) and 2 (C)-CH ₂ -(C)	95.2
<i>iso</i> Butyl chloride CH ₃ } CH. CH ₂ .Cl CH ₃ }	228.4	0.5	2 CH ₃ -(C) and (C) } CH-(C) (C) }	95.3
<i>n</i> -Amyl chloride CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₃ .CH ₂ .Cl	270.4	0.7	CH ₃ -(C) and 3 (C)-CH ₂ -(C)	95.1
<i>iso</i> Amyl chloride CH ₃ } CH. CH ₂ .CH ₂ .Cl CH ₃ }	269.8	0.7	2 CH ₃ -(C), (C) } CH-(C) (C) } and (C)-CH ₂ -(C)	96.7
				Mean 95.6

The values obtained from the structural method and those from Sugden's method are compared with the observed parachor values in Table IV. Structural parachor method shows better agreement with the experimental values.

TABLE IV

Compound.	<i>P</i> (Structural method).	<i>P</i> _{obs.}	<i>P</i> (Sugden's method).
Ethyl chloride	151.0	151.6	149.4
<i>n</i> -Propyl chloride	190.9	190.2	188.4
<i>n</i> -Butyl chloride	230.9	230.5	227.4
<i>iso</i> Butyl chloride	228.7	228.4	227.4
<i>n</i> -Amyl chloride	270.9	270.4	266.4
<i>iso</i> Amyl chloride	268.7	269.8	266.4

TABLE V

Group parachor for (C)—CH₂. Br

Compound.	<i>P</i> _{obs.}	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	<i>P</i> for (C)—CH ₂ —Br _n
Ethyl bromide CH ₃ —CH ₂ . Br	165.7	0.2	CH ₃ —(C)	110.3
<i>n</i> -Propyl bromide CH ₃ —CH ₂ —CH ₂ . Br	205.3	0.4	CH ₃ —(C) and (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	109.9
<i>n</i> -Butyl bromide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₂ —CH ₂ . Br	243.5	0.6	CH ₃ —(C) and 2 (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	108.1
<i>iso</i> Butyl bromide CH ₃ } CH—CH ₂ . Br CH ₃ }	243.8	0.6	2 CH ₃ —(C) and (C) } CH—(C) (C) }	110.6
<i>n</i> -Amyl bromide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₃ —CH ₂ . Br	283.6	0.8	CH ₃ —(C), 3 (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	108.2
<i>iso</i> -Amyl bromide CH ₃ } CH—CH ₂ —CH ₂ . Br CH ₃ }	282.9	0.8	2 CH ₃ —(C), (C)—CH ₂ —(C) and (C) } CH—(C) (C) }	109.7
<i>n</i> -Hexyl bromide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₄ —CH ₂ . Br	322.8	1.0	CH ₃ —(C) and 4 (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	107.4
<i>n</i> -Heptyl bromide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₅ —CH ₂ . Br	363.0	1.2	CH ₃ —(C) and 5 (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	107.6
<i>n</i> -Octyl bromide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₆ —CH ₂ . Br	402.4	1.5	CH ₃ —(C) and 6 (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	106.9
				Mean 108.7

The parachor values obtained from structural method and from Sugden's method are compared with the observed values. The structural values are in better agreement with the observed values compared to Sugden's method (Table VI).

TABLE VI

Compound.	Parachor values (<i>P</i>)		Sugden's method.
	Structural method.	Observed.	
Ethyl bromide	164.1	165.7	163.1
<i>n</i> -Propyl bromide	204.1	205.3	202.1
<i>n</i> -Butyl bromide	244.1	243.5	241.1
<i>iso</i> Butyl bromide	241.9	243.8	241.1
<i>n</i> -Amyl bromide	284.1	283.6	280.1
<i>iso</i> Amyl bromide	281.9	282.9	280.1
<i>n</i> -Hexyl bromide	324.1	322.8	319.1
<i>n</i> -Heptyl bromide	364.1	363.0	358.1
<i>n</i> -Octyl bromide	404.2	402.4	397.1

TABLE VII

Compound.	Group parachor for (C)—CH ₂ —I.			P for (C)—CH ₂ , I.
	P _{obs.}	E. C	Groups subtracted.	
Ethyl iodide CH ₃ —CH ₂ I	187.0	0.3	CH ₃ —(C)	131.5
<i>n</i> -Propyl iodide CH ₃ —CH ₂ —CH ₂ I	226.0	0.5	CH—(C) and (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	130.5
<i>n</i> -Butyl iodide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₂ —CH ₂ I	264.7	0.7	CH ₃ —(C) and 2 (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	129.2
<i>iso</i> Butyl iodide $\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CH} \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}$ —CH ₂ I	265.0	0.7	2 CH ₃ —(C), $\begin{array}{l} \text{(C)} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CH} \\ \diagup \\ \text{(C)} \end{array}$ —(C)	131.7
<i>n</i> -Hexyl iodide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₄ —CH ₂ I	344.1	1.1	CH ₃ —(C), 4(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	128.6
<i>n</i> -Heptyl iodide CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₅ —CH ₂ I	384.5	1.5	CH ₃ —C, 5(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	128.8
			Mean	130.05 or 130.1

The structural parachor values and those obtained from Sugden's method are compared with those of the observed values (Table VIII).

TABLE VIII

Compound.	Parachor values (P)		
	Structural.	Observed.	Sugden's.
Ethyl iodide	185.6	187.0	186.1
<i>n</i> -Propyl iodide	225.6	226.0	225.1
<i>n</i> -Butyl iodide	265.6	264.7	264.1
<i>iso</i> Butyl iodide	263.4	265.0	264.1
<i>n</i> -Hexyl iodide	345.6	344.1	342.1
<i>n</i> -Heptyl iodide	385.8	384.5	381.1

In spite of the better results obtained by Gibling's method it has to be noted that the group parachor does not seem to be a true constant, but varies in the same homologous series as we pass from one member to another. Thus, the value of (C)—CH₂—NH₂ group continuously increases as the number of carbon atoms in the chain increases. In case of alkyl chlorides same is true for (C)—CH₂—Cl, although the first member, ethyl chloride shows anomalous behaviour. On the other hand, the value for (C)—CH₂—Br group from alkyl bromide falls as we ascend the series. The first member, ethyl bromide and *iso*-butyl bromide with branch chain show anomalous behaviour. The observations for (C)—CH₂—I group from alkyl iodide are very similar to those of (C)—CH₂—Br group.